

Empirical energy levels and line lists of nine stable water isotopologues
from the analysis of far infrared absorption spectra
at SOLEIL synchrotron

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Water vapour absorbs infrared radiation!...

John Tyndall, Phil Mag, (1861)

On the Absorption and Radiation of Heat by Gases and Vapours, and on the Physical Connexion of Radiation, Absorption, and Conduction

Clear sky conditions

Absorption spectroscopy of molecules

$$I_{out} = I_{in} \exp(-\alpha L)$$

Absorption spectroscopy of molecules

$$I_{out} = I_{in} \exp(-\alpha L)$$

$$\alpha(\nu) = N S \Phi(\nu)$$

Gas concentration

Line intensity

$$\int \alpha(\nu) d\nu = N S$$

$$cm^{-1} \times cm^{-1} = molecule/cm^3 \times cm/molecule$$

$P_{water} = 11.8$ Torr

Evacuated cell

Clear sky conditions

Clear sky conditions

FORUM range:
100-667 cm^{-1}
or 100-16 μm
or 3-19 THz

UV

Visible

Infrared

0.2

1

10

60

Position inaccuracies in the FIR have an impact in all the spectral ranges!

Fourier transform spectroscopie (FTS)

Far-infrared range

50-700 cm^{-1} | 14-200 μm | 1.5-21THz

FTS

4 campaigns

(2014) and 2017: self-continuum

2018: foreign-continuum

2021: Lines *September 26th - October 4th*

Thanks to O. Pirali

White-type cell $L = 2.5 \text{ m} \rightarrow L_{\text{abs}} = 151 \text{ m}$

Bolometer detection

Frequency range 50 – 750 cm^{-1}

Temperature ≈ 294 K

Optical path length $L=151.75$ m

Resolution 0.002-0.001 cm^{-1}

About 10 hours/spectrum

List of the recordings

Molecule	Pressure range	Nb of P
Natural water	0.12 mTorr – 5.2 Torr	5
41% H ₂ ¹⁷ O, 27% H ₂ ¹⁸ O, 22% H ₂ ¹⁶ O	15 mTorr – 2.9 Torr	4
50% D ₂ O 20.5% H ₂ ¹⁷ O 13.5% H ₂ ¹⁸ O 11% H ₂ ¹⁶ O	13.5 mTorr- 6 Torr	5
D ₂ O	15 mTorr – 6 Torr	4
50% H ₂ ¹⁶ O 50% D ₂ O	22.5 mTorr – 3 Torr	3

JQSRT2022

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vapor absorption spectroscopy and validation tests of databases in the far-infrared (50–720 cm⁻¹). Part 1: Natural water

M. Toureille^a, A.O. Koroleva^{a,b}, S.N. Mikhailenko^{c,d}, O. Pirali^{e,f}, A. Campargue^{a,*}

Check for updates

Statistical distribution of the isotopes! H₂O+D₂O <--> 2HDO

Molecule	Pressure range	Nb of P
Natural water	0.12 mTorr – 5.25 Torr	5
41% H ₂ ¹⁷ O, 27% H ₂ ¹⁸ O, 22% H ₂ ¹⁶ O	15 mTorr – 2.89 Torr	4
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D ₂ O	15 mTorr – 6 Torr	4
50% H ₂ ¹⁶ O 50% D ₂ O	22.5 mTorr – 3 Torr	3

JQSRT2022

JQSRT2024

JQSRT2025

JPCRD2024

JPCRD 2025

Statistical distribution of the isotopes! H₂O+D₂O <--> 2HDO

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Empirical energy levels and line lists of D₂¹⁷O, and D₂¹⁸O from the analysis of far infrared absorption spectra (50–720 cm⁻¹)

AIP Publishing

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Empirical energy levels and line lists of HD¹⁷O and HD¹⁸O from the analysis of far infrared absorption spectra

S. N. Mikhailenko, A. O. Koroleva, and A. Campargue

Article

The Far-Infrared Absorption Spectrum of HD¹⁶O: Experimental Line Positions, Accurate Empirical Energy Levels, and a Recommended Line List

Semen N. Mikhailenko ¹

Line list construction

Natural water

Spectrum	Pressure	Lines nb
#1	1.28 mTorr	804
#2	0.06 Torr	1778
#3	0.86 Torr	1987
#4	5.25 Torr	1367
#5	0.12 mTorr	306

Line list construction

Natural water

$$T_{trans} = I_{out} / I_{in} = \exp(-\alpha L)$$

$\alpha(\nu) = N S \Phi(\nu)$

Gas concentration Line intensity

$\int \alpha(\nu) d\nu = N S$

$cm^{-1} \times cm^{-1} = molecule/cm^3 \times cm/molecule$

Natural water

2867 water lines

Intensities > 2×10^{-26} cm/molecule

Intensities span > 5 orders of magnitude.

Ro-vibration assignments by S. Mikhailenko

using literature and Schwenke and Partridge predictions available at <https://spectra.iao.ru>

At 300 K, $kT= 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$

$$000J''K_a''K_c'' \rightarrow 000J'K_a'K_c'$$

$$010J''K_a''K_c'' \rightarrow 010J'K_a'K_c'$$

+

some (020)-(020) in H_2O species and also a few transitions involving (100) and (001) for D_2O species

Global line list

Assignments

Natural water

Tourelle et al. JQSRT2022

Statistics of the rovibrational assignments of the five spectra of natural water recorded at SOLEIL at various pressures up to 7 mbar.

Molecule	NT^a	NT_{new}^b	J	K_a
$H_2^{16}O$	1310	96 (385)	22	14
$H_2^{18}O$	564	3 (3)	18	12
$H_2^{17}O$	407	3 (3)	17	10
$HD^{16}O$	674	46 (63)	19	12
$HD^{18}O$	42		10	7
$HD^{17}O$	4		6	4
Total	3001	148 (454)	22	14

Notes:

^a Number of assigned transitions.

^b Number of newly observed transitions. The first number considers previous studies by absorption and emission. The number between parenthesis considers only absorption studies.

spc	Nu_exp	dN	S_exp	dS
3	118.04454	5	1.869E-24	6
3	165.07328	5	1.435E-24	3
3	168.09872	11	2.589E-25	11
3	173.65217	8	8.392E-25	8
3	174.36575	5	7.695E-25	4
3	185.67453	5	1.807E-24	3
3	200.72759	5	3.778E-24	5
3	220.52085	5	1.150E-24	3
3	235.59390	5	4.761E-25	7
3	236.92234	7	3.869E-25	6
3	258.66921	5	3.136E-24	3
2	291.44779	5	2.479E-23	3
1	302.64445	5	1.114E-21	3
3	309.78911	5	5.228E-24	3

HITRAN2020													
Nu	S	assignment						d1	Ratio_1				
118.044535	1.997E-24	000	14	6	8	000	14	5	9	1	0.936		
165.073002	1.598E-24	000	14	7	7	000	14	6	8	28	0.898		
168.098288	2.399E-25	000	15	5	11	000	14	6	8	43	1.079		
173.652719	8.024E-25	000	15	6	10	000	15	5	11	-55	1.046		
174.365673	7.317E-25	000	14	6	8	000	13	7	7	8	1.052		
185.673836	1.911E-24	000	15	5	11	000	15	4	12	69	0.946		
200.727999	4.003E-24	000	13	8	6	000	13	7	7	-41	0.944		
220.519932	1.041E-24	000	14	9	6	000	14	8	7	92	1.105		
235.592641	4.969E-25	000	13	10	4	000	13	9	5	126	1.105		
236.922838	3.507E-25	000	14	10	5	000	14	9	6	126	1.105		
258.668316	3.176E-24	000	16	2	14	000	16	2	15	126	1.105		
291.448007	2.408E-23	000	16	2	15	000	16	2	15	126	1.105		
302.644081	9.033E-22	000	16	2	15	000	16	2	15	126	1.105		
309.789058	5.544E-24	000	14	9	6	000	14	8	7	92	1.105		

W2020										
Nu	t	dN1	S	d2	Ratio_2	R	d3			
118.04673	M	4	2.002E-24	-219	0.934	54.8	-9			
165.07126	M	35	1.601E-24	202	0.896	5.8	1			
168.09575	M	16	2.405E-25	297	1.077	18.6	-8			
173.65311	M	20	8.044E-25	-94	1.043	4.7	1			
174.36787	M	11	7.338E-25	-212	1.049	19.3	-3			
185.67350	M	14	1.916E-24	103	0.943	7.4	-2			
200.73021	M	17	4.013E-24	-262	0.941	15.4	3			
235.59157	M	6	1.043E-24	143	1.103	23.8	4			
236.92358	M	33	4.983E-25	233	0.955	7.1	-9			
258.66827	M	35	3.516E-25	-124	1.100	3.5	0			
291.44889	M	14	3.184E-24	94	0.985	6.7	5			
302.64423	M	8	2.415E-23	-110	1.027	13.8	10			
309.78917	M	3	9.059E-22	122	0.922	40.7	-16			
		8	5.560E-24	-106	0.940	13.3	14			

Overall good agreement

H₂¹⁶O

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Analysis of the high-resolution water spectrum up to the Second Triad and to $J = 30$

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Journal of Physical and Chemical Reference Data

The W2020 Database of Validated Rovibrational Experimental Transitions and Empirical Energy Levels of Water Isotopologues. II. H₂¹⁷O and H₂¹⁸O with an Update to H₂¹⁶O

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¹Tibor Furtenbacher, ¹Roland Tóbiás, ¹Jonathan Tennyson, Oleg L. Polyansky, Aleksandra A. Kyuberis, Roman I. Ovsyannikov, Nikolay F. Zobov, and ¹Attila G. Császár

W2020 inaccuracies

Both HITRAN and W2020 inaccuracies

Experimental position accuracy of $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for well isolated lines

- 460 and 99 transitions of $H_2^{17}O$ and $HD^{17}O$ transitions newly observed by absorption
- 69 $H_2^{17}O$ and 20 $HD^{17}O$ energy levels newly determined.

H₂17O

Significantly better agreement for the W2020 line positions

HITRAN2020: Gordon IE, et al. The HITRAN2020 molecular spectroscopic database. JQSRT 2022;277:107949.

W2020: Furtenbacher T, et al. W2020: a database of validated rovibrational experimental transitions and empirical energy levels of water isotopologues. II. H₂17O and H₂18O with an update to H₂16O. JPS RD 2020;49:043103.

14CoMaPi: Coudert LH, Martin-Drumel M-A, Pirali O. Analysis of the high-resolution water spectrum up to the second triad. J Mol Spectrosc 2014;303:36–41.

HD¹⁶O

Article

The Far-Infrared Absorption Spectrum of HD¹⁶O: Experimental Line Positions, Accurate Empirical Energy Levels, and a Recommended Line List

Semen N. Mikhailenko ¹, Ekaterina V. Karlovets ^{2,3}, Aleksandra O. Koroleva ^{2,4} and Alain Campargue ^{2,*}

Table 5. General information on the HD¹⁶O transitions assigned in the three analyze 50 and 720 cm⁻¹.

Band	NT ^a	J _{max}	K _{a max}
(000)–(000)	1778	25	14
(010)–(010)	617	18	11
(020)–(020)	18	9	6
(100)–(100)	30	9	8
Total	2443	25	14

^a number of assigned transitions.

Over 2443 transitions assigned about 1900 are newly observed by absorption

HD¹⁶O

HD¹⁷O

(000)

HD¹⁸O

(010)

- Absorption literature
- Emission
- SOLEIL

HD₁₆₀

Improvement on the uncertainty of the energy levels

IUPAC:
Tennyson, et al. *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transf.* **2010**, 111, 2160–2184

The far infrared absorption spectrum of D₂¹⁶O, D₂¹⁷O,
and D₂¹⁸O: Experimental line positions, empirical
energy levels and recommended line lists

S. N. Mikhailenko, E. V. Karlovets, A. O. Koroleva, and A. Campargue

Available Online: pubs.aip.org/aip/jpr

10396 transitions of the 9 stable isotopologues

TABLE 2. Statistics of assigned water transitions

Molecule	Factor ^a (%)	NT ^b	J_{\max}	$K_a \max$
H ₂ ¹⁶ O	4.0	679	18	12
H ₂ ¹⁷ O	0.1	351	16	10
H ₂ ¹⁸ O	0.1	331	15	10
HD ¹⁶ O	25	1924	24	14
HD ¹⁷ O	1	1000	22	12
HD ¹⁸ O	1	968	21	12
D ₂ ¹⁶ O	100	2886	29	18
D ₂ ¹⁷ O	2	1088	25	14
D ₂ ¹⁸ O	2	1169	25	16

Conclusion

- The analysis of the 21 spectra recorded at SOLEIL 4 years ago is now completed
- *Large amount of new FIR transitions and energy levels have been obtained using SOLEIL synchrotron (spectral coverage, more than 10^3 sensitivity gain, position accuracy on the order of $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)*
- Validation tests of the existing databases (HITRAN, W2020-2024)
- Corrections in the FIR have an impact in all the spectral ranges!
- Current work: elaboration of a recommended list for natural water in the FIR
 - empirical positions with their uncertainties,
 - *ab initio* intensities,
 - ?line profile broadening parameters?

S. Mikhailenko

A. Koroleva
E. Karlovets
A. Campargue

Merci

O. Pirali

The far-infrared spectrum of ^{18}O enriched water vapour (40–700 cm^{-1})

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Water vapor absorption spectroscopy and validation tests of databases in the far-infrared (50–720 cm^{-1}). Part 1: Natural water

Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy & Radiative Transfer 314 (2024) 108829

Water vapor absorption spectroscopy and validation tests of databases in the far-infrared (50–720 cm^{-1}). Part 2: H_2^{17}O and HD^{17}O

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Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy & Radiative Transfer 347 (2025) 109638

Empirical energy levels and line lists of D_2^{17}O , and D_2^{18}O from the analysis of far infrared absorption spectra (50–720 cm^{-1})

S.N. Mikhailenko^a, A.O. Koroleva^{b,c}, A. Campargue^{b,*}

The far infrared absorption spectrum of D_2^{16}O , D_2^{17}O , and D_2^{18}O : Experimental line positions, empirical energy levels and recommended line lists

S. N. Mikhailenko, E. V. Karlovets, A. O. Koroleva, and A. Campargue

Available Online: pubs.aip.org/aip/jpr

Empirical energy levels and line lists of HD^{17}O and HD^{18}O from the analysis of far infrared absorption spectra

S. N. Mikhailenko, A. O. Koroleva, and A. Campargue

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Article

The Far-Infrared Absorption Spectrum of HD^{16}O : Experimental Line Positions, Accurate Empirical Energy Levels, and a Recommended Line List

Semen N. Mikhailenko¹, Ekaterina V. Karlovets^{2,3}, Aleksandra O. Koroleva^{2,4} and Alain Campargue^{2,*}